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INTERNATIONAL WOMEN' S DAY: CELEBRATION OR PROTEST?

ENGLISH VERSION

International Women's Day: Celebration or Protest?

Let us celebrate and protest. On March 8 especially, but every day as well. It is fair, necessary, and indispensable.

As International Women's Day is commemorated, opinions begin to diverge on whether this is a date for celebration, protest, strike action, or any other initiative emerging from feminist grassroots movements. The fundamental question is this: is it a massive celebration or a massive protest?

Let us take a broader perspective.

We know that women make up slightly more than half of the world's population. We also know that real equality remains far from being achieved. Every day we witness all kinds of violence inflicted upon women of all ages—from selective abortions in countries such as China, India, and much of the Muslim world, to femicides and rape, as well as inequality in opportunities for education and employment, including wage gaps of 30 to 40 percent compared to men with equal or even lesser qualifications performing the same tasks.

It becomes evident, then, that protest is necessary.

We must protest privately and publicly, individually and collectively, in every arena where it is required and in every way possible. Every day of the year.

Yet March 8, the one day specifically devoted to reflecting upon the condition of women, is the ideal occasion to take to the streets and publicly draw society's attention to our inequalities. Protest is legitimate when it demands justice.

Not only is protest legitimate—it is indispensable if popular will is to emerge and later become political will, and if that political will is to result in legislation that enables progress. It is equally essential to ensure that existing laws are made known and enforced in every sphere of human activity.

This March 8, and every day we can, let us protest.

We also know that the struggle for women's rights did not begin with this inspiring generation of the green wave.

Not at all.

Women who have fought individually and collectively have always existed. Their efforts have been so systematically erased by official historiography that the very existence of some of our predecessors in women's empowerment—and even their contributions—has at times been doubted.

Each of these women's contributions forms part of a valuable chain of progress that has made possible the emergence of this new generation of feminists, full of strength and hope, with great achievements and, undoubtedly, some mistakes—as is true of every human movement.

Since ancient times, echoes of women's struggles have reached us: Lysistrata, who led a sex strike to end war in the fifth century BCE; Hypatia of Alexandria, philosopher and mathematician of the third century CE; and the Roman matrons, considered one of history's earliest examples of women's collective strike action.

Later came the French women, pioneers in women's access to culture through aristocratic salons and leaders of the French Revolution.

There were numerous women-led demands and strikes, such as those of the New York shirtwaist workers in 1906, the Women's Day Off in Iceland in 1975, and many, many others.

Let us not forget one of the best-known women's labor strikes: the 1912 "Bread and Roses" strike.

The women workers of Lawrence, Massachusetts, demanded "bread," but also "roses," as a symbol of a dignified life.

Among individual figures, to mention only a few: Clara Zetkin, Rosa Luxemburg, Alexandra Kollontai, Simone de Beauvoir, and Flora Tristan.

Collectively, let us remember the American and British suffragists, the Spanish Republican women, women artists throughout history, the French feminists of May 1968, and the Spanish Feminist Party, founded during the final years of Franco's brutally misogynistic dictatorship.

In Latin America, collective struggles have combined with and strengthened individual acts of empowerment, as seen in the example of the Indigenous leader and shaman Prudencia Ayala, who ran for the presidency of El Salvador in 1930, Matilde Hidalgo, who exercised her right to vote in Ecuador in 1929, Nobel Peace Prize laureate Rigoberta Menchú, and naturally the struggles of countless artists such as Frida Kahlo and Violeta Parra.

The list is endless.

Across the planet, the massive demonstrations of March 8 and other days of women's struggle would not exist without those predecessors.

In our own country, outstanding pioneers include Julieta Lanteri, the anarcho-feminist América Scarfó, Alicia Moreau de Justo, and more recently Eva Perón and the women of the Female

Branch, the generation that continued and culminated the struggle for suffrage—a remarkable generation that taught Argentine women how to vote and politically empowered them.

It is therefore right to celebrate.

It is not only an act of strict justice owed to women who risked—and sometimes lost—their lives, freedom, careers, or families so that you and I might enjoy ever greater rights.

Let us be conscious of the progress achieved through women's individual and collective efforts throughout history, and let us celebrate.

Let us be fair and compassionate toward our predecessors, and let us celebrate.

Let us be fair and compassionate toward those who, for centuries and decades, have fought so that today, young feminist, you may have received the education that leads you to the streets to demand your rights.

Let us celebrate.

And let us protest.

On March 8 especially—but every day as well.

It is fair. It is necessary. It is indispensable.